

Dimas Vega RPB , Pramana Rafif, Abdullah Yusuf, Ahmad Syafi'i
“Talk” an AI-Powered Speaking Partner Application
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1st Dimas Vega Rizqyqa Putra Budiyo, 2nd Pramana Rafif, 3rd Abdullah Yusuf,
4th Ahmad Syafi'i
English Language Teaching Department
STKIP Al Hikmah Surabaya
Surabaya, Indonesia
1st vegadimas55@gmail.com
2nd rafifpramana1@gmail.com
3rd yusufabdullah515@gmail.com
4th ahmadsyafii20@gmail.com

***Abstract:** With the advancement of technology, there are currently numerous tools and applications that are designed to facilitate students in improving their English speaking skills (Chun et al., 2016). One of these tools is called TALK. TALK is an online platform which is designed to help users improve their spoken English skills. It utilizes advanced speech recognition technology to provide users with feedback on their pronunciation, intonation, and overall spoken language proficiency.*

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Speaking, TALK Application

INTRODUCTION

English, as the language used in the realm of international communication, has increasingly become a prerequisite and a benchmark to determine whether someone is considered capable of mastering the understanding of the global world or not (Mukminin et al., 2019). An individual's proficiency level in the English language now serves as a fundamental guide to assess their credibility across various fields, ranging from education, business, economics, even to politics and science (Muniroh et al., 2023). This phenomenon is not hard to find, and one barometer is the growing number of job vacancies that require applicants to achieve a certain level of English proficiency before being recruited into a company.

Another example is evident in the field of education. A student that aspiring to pursue higher studies is greatly influenced by their English language abilities. A student may receive scholarship opportunities or other conveniences, based on their proficiency in English. Particularly in countries such as Indonesia, where English is still considered a foreign language, with less than 40% of the population proficient in English (Rukmi & Khasanah, 2020). The English Proficiency Index of 2022 that is released by EF Education First ranked Indonesia at the number of 81 from 111 countries assessed for their population's English language skills. Consequently, with these facts, English proficiency in Indonesia is still perceived as a rarity for the majority of the population.

This fact highlights the increasing need for effective and accessible English education. Many schools and educational institutions are now developing modern and innovative methods for teaching English, encompassing both teaching approaches and tools that facilitate learners in enhancing their English language skills (Cong-Lem, 2018). In learning English, there are four essential competencies that must be mastered by the learners. These four competencies are proficiency in reading, listening, writing, and speaking (Pliushchenko & Zaslavskiy, 2021). However, the speaking skill is often considered as the most crucial among the other four abilities. Speaking is one of the most important skills of all four language skills, because individuals who learn a language are referred to as the speakers of that language. The main aim of English language teaching is to give learners the ability to use English language effectively and correctly in communication (Jarrín & Kim, 2019).

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Speaking is a fundamental aspect of language acquisition, serving as a pivotal skill that can be honed through the deliberate expansion of one's vocabulary. It is a dynamic process encompassing the art of constructing and articulating meaning through the proficient utilization of words and non-verbal cues within various contexts (Constrained et al., 2019). In essence, speaking is a multifaceted act that transcends the mere vocalization of words. The mastery of speaking skills necessitates a comprehensive understanding of the cultural and social dimensions that influence language use.

However, from this speaking ability, there is one crucial element known as oral proficiency. English oral proficiency refers to an individual's ability to communicate effectively in spoken English. It involves the skill of expressing oneself clearly, fluently, and appropriately in oral communication (Vančová, 2022). Individuals often seek to improve their English oral proficiency for personal and professional development, because English oral proficiency is a crucial aspect of language competence, in both social and professional contexts.

Thus, with the advancement of technology, there are currently numerous tools and applications that are designed to facilitate students in improving their English speaking skills (Chun et al., 2016). One of these tools is called TALK. TALK is an online platform which is designed to help users improve their spoken English skills. It utilizes advanced speech recognition technology to provide users with feedback on their pronunciation, intonation, and overall spoken language proficiency (Mayor, 2021).

LITERATURE REVIEW

TALK APPLICATION

“Talk English Speaking Practice” is a free application that helps you improve your English speaking skills. This app has various features to help you learn and practice speaking English include Interactive Conversation Lesson then Conversations with Native Speakers and the last features is Quizzes and Games

In this application there are many themes related to everyday life, therefore it really helps users so they can learn and immediately practice them in real life.

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not only does it provide lots of conversations, but in the application we not only learn about speaking but also focus on listening because in this application there are native people who will help us on how to pronounce a sentence well and correctly

After hearing the native speaker's conversation, the user is asked first to do a quiz so that the user feels they understand what the native speaker was talking about

and then finally the great thing about this application is that after the user feels they understand how the native speaks and understands what is being said, the last part of this application is practice in pronunciation so there are 2 sessions where the user will role play as the

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one in the conversation. practice: The user will be trained first regarding speed in speaking English, which is adjusted to the application, then secondly, recording, namely the user is asked to record your voice.

CONCLUSION

With the advancement of technology, there are currently numerous tools and applications that are designed to facilitate students in improving their English speaking skills (Chun et al., 2016). One of these tools is called TALK. TALK is an online platform which is designed to help users improve their spoken English skills. It utilizes advanced speech recognition technology to provide users with feedback on their pronunciation, intonation, and overall spoken language proficiency.

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